

Evaluation of potency of sweetness of a natural plant based drug, *Stevia rebaudiana* with human subjects from cultivated field of Shimoga, Karnataka

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The aim of this present field study was to evaluate the relation between soil pH and sweetener effect of crude *Stevia* extracts by applied bio-fertilizers and also to determine the variation on the relative sweetness of *Stevia* [*Stevia rebaudiana* (Bert.) Bertoni, F; Asteraceae] leaf extract (SrB) collected by month intervals from the field using magnitude estimation. Results showed sweetness potency in terms of the times of sweeter than standard sucrose (3.0% w/v) was not having any significant variation in between the months ($P > 0.05$) but significantly differs with the applied biofertilizers ($P < 0.001$) in the field. Further it has shown that the sweetness potency negatively correlated with soil pH ($r = -0.743^{**}$, significant at 1%) and positively correlated with dried leaf biomass and amount present of stevioside in the extract. The sweet potency of crude extract resulted nearly 50 times more than 3.0% sucrose solution at lower pH. The results show that the sweetness potency of *Stevia* crude extract completely depends on agronomical practice, method of extraction, refining of crude extract and pH of the soil.

Keywords: Biofertilizers, soil pH, *Stevia rebaudiana*, secondary metabolites, sweet potency.

Introduction

Stevia rebaudiana, commonly known as honey plant in Indian due to having sweet nature which is sweeter than sugar and has less carbohydrate and calories. The plant belongs to Asteraceae family and native of Brazil and Paraguay of South America¹. Further the plant has domesticated in India during late 20th Century. Due to its versatile medicinal applications such as antioxidant², antidiabetic², antihypertension³, anti-inflammatory activity⁴, wound healing⁵, anticancer properties⁶ and many other therapeutic applications gave *Stevia*, a focused plant in an herbal world. Not only medicinal activities but also used as natural bio-sweetener as non caloric in nature. The main useful part is leaf and it contains mainly steviol glycosides viz. stevioside, rebaudioside A-S (Fig. 1), dulcosides and traces of volatile oil⁷. Chemically they are enkurine glycosides with the sugar group attachments. Depends on sugar group the sweetness activity is varies. With these multiple role, *Stevia* is now become a promising natural herb in this current era. Recently it is use as sugar supplement in many food products, nutraceutical preparations because of 300 to 450 times sweeter than sugar⁸ and various

cosmetic preparations especially as skin moisturizers⁹. Furthermore it is safe for the diabetic patients because it is non caloric but sweet in nature. Many Indian herbal companies are using *Stevia* leaf powder, refining as per standardized methods and used in many food products, soft drinks, candies, bakery items etc.¹⁰. Commercially the leaf is sold in market in tea bags, in white powder forms and many others. These days' commercial applications of *Stevia* economically enhanced the market demand in world market. As per the current record, the demand of *Stevia* in world market was 336 million USD in 2014 which may cross 486 million USD in 2017¹¹. In Asian countries, Japan is the highest producer followed by China and India. The market share of Japan is about 25% of total *Stevia* in world market where as India's stand in below 12%. Hence awareness about *Stevia* in India is most essential to reduce health problems. Based on that, the present study was carried out with the new innovation towards the determination of sweet potency by magnitude estimation with scaling method vis a vis increase of biomass yield with the application of bio-fertilizers and the impact of stevioside content and soil pH on sweet potency.

Fig. 1. Chemistry of secondary metabolites of *Stevia* plant.

Materials and method:

A field experiment was conducted in the month of November 2010 at the Shimoga in acid soil (Fig. 2). Before start of the experiment, initial soil pH was analyzed. Soil pH was determined by pH meter (Elico, India) by preparing solution with ratio of soil:water, 1:2.5 w/v. The soil pH was found 6.10. Further experiment was conducted as per the standard procedure design by the agronomist Dr. T. N. Shivananda, Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Bangalore. Experimental design as per follows (Table 1).

Table 1. Preparation of the experimental bed for *Stevia* cultivation

Treatments	Application of bio-fertilizers
Control	Without application of bio-fertilizers
PSB	Application of 250 g of PSB
AZO	Application of 250 g of AZO
VAM	Application of 500 g of VAM
AZO + VAM	Application of 250 g of AZO and 500 g of VAM
PSB + AZO	Application of 250 g of PSB and 250 g of AZO
PSB + VAM	Application of 250 g of PSB and 500 g of VAM
P + V + A	Application of 250 g of PSB, 250 g of AZO and 500 g of VAM

PSB = Phosphate solubilising bacteria, AZO = Azospirillum, VAM = Vesicular arbuscular mycorrhiza, V + P + A = VAM + PSB + AZO

Preparation of extract:

An aqueous extraction was performed for air dried *Stevia* leaves. Leaves were soaked with 2 g of CaCO₃ at pH 10 to remove the impurities. Then sample was refluxed with water for 4 h after standardized the method. Finally crude extract was collected after filtration followed by rotary flash evaporation at 45°C. Same process was followed for all individual

Fig. 2. Experimental zone.

extract preparation. All the extracts were stored in well closed glass bottles at kept for refrigeration condition at 4°C before sweetness study.

Method for HPLC analysis: Crude extract and standard Stevioside samples were dissolved separately as per required concentration. C18 column was used with the mobile phase methanol and water (7:3) and detected in 210 nm at UV.

Then both samples injected 10 µL to the HPLC column as per the method described by Bovanova *et al.*¹².

Determination of sweetness level for each treatment of Stevia, cultivated under acidic soil zone:

Materials: *Stevia* leaves were collected individually from all the beds of the cultivated area and cumulatively six month leaf samples of *Stevia* were stored separately and finally dried the leaves in oven temperature of 45°C.

Sample and standard preparation: Distilled water was used to make concentration of 3.0% (3 g of extract in 100 ml of water) of all extracted crude *Stevia* samples. At the same 3.0% sucrose solution was prepared by mixing with water and was used as standard. This standard was available to the 10 trained subjects for rinsing purposes. All the solutions were prepared 24 h before testing and held in the dark at room temperature in glass bottles. All solutions were prepared freshly.

Procedure:

Ten trained panelists were used for this present study (under the supervision of Dr. Sobha Rani R. H., Al-Ameen College of Pharmacy, Bangalore). All panelists have been exposed to a variety of sweeteners prior to the study. Subjects were well trained in the scaling procedures for this study. Panelists were presented first with a reference solution containing 3.0% (w/v) sucrose, to taste. The reference (3.0% sucrose solution) was assigned an arbitrary sweetness value of 10. They were then presented with the test samples using sip and swallow procedure and instructed to assign a sweetness score relative to the reference. Panelists were requested to assign numbers which reflected on sensory intensity. For example, a score of 20 indicate a sample two fold sweeter than the reference, whereas a value of 5 should be half as sweet as the reference. Immediately after providing magnitude estimation for sweetness, panelists rated the samples for relative sweetness using a 0–10 point's scale where 0 meant absence of the sweet taste and 10 indicated it was extremely intense¹³. All samples were tasted randomly.

Statistical analysis: One way ANOVA followed by Dunnett multiple comparison tests was performed using Graph Pad Prism 5 software to compare all the treatments with control treatment and the results are presented as the means ± S.E.M., with the critical level of significance set at P < 0.05.

Results and discussion

Stevia aqueous extracts (crude extract) prepared from *Stevia* dried powder (collected individual month wise) and the taste intensity was recorded as per panelists performance and the results was tabulated in Table 2 and show the sweet intensity for all the extracts nearly fifty times more than that of standard sucrose solution (3.0%). Results revealed at lower pH value i.e. at pH 5.87, the sweet intensity showed higher with their respective treatments. With the treatment of AZO, the intensity of sweetness was 495±18.93** (pH 5.88) in the first month but later on decreased. Interestingly, with the treatment of P + V + A, the sweet intensity constantly maintained more than 52 times and the value were higher in first month, 535±22.42** (at pH 5.89) followed by 530±18.56** (at pH 5.87) in fourth month. Results of pH estimation, fresh biomass and stevioside contain were also recorded and were tabulated in Tables 3, 4 and 5 respectively.

Table 3. pH estimation of the soil

Treatments	Experiments in months					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
T ₁ , Control	6.10	6.05	6.03	6.07	6.08	6.06
T ₂ , PSB	6.00	6.03	6.06	6.05	6.06	6.07
T ₃ , AZO	5.90	6.07	6.03	6.07	6.08	6.08
T ₄ , VAM	6.00	6.02	6.03	6.06	6.07	6.10
T ₅ , V + A	5.90	6.08	6.10	6.08	6.09	6.07
T ₆ , P + A	5.90	6.07	6.06	6.06	6.06	6.08
T ₇ , V + P	6.10	6.05	5.96	6.07	6.07	6.06
T ₈ , V + P + A	5.90	6.05	6.03	6.08	6.06	6.06
CD (P = 0.05)	4.20	3.32	3.10	3.06	3.08	3.14

PSB = Phosphate solubilising bacteria, AZO = Azospirillum, VAM = Vesicular Arbuscular mycorrhiza, V + P + A = VAM + PSB + AZO.

Table 4. Fresh biomass determination

Treatments	Experiments in months					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
T ₁ , Control	400	560	648	694	720	740
T ₂ , PSB	460	610	720	756	798	810
T ₃ , AZO	470	670	750	750	765	783
T ₄ , VAM	380	612	690	798	822	859
T ₅ , V + A	473	720	765	790	822	836
T ₆ , P + A	495	690	770	816	836	855
T ₇ , V + P	468	620	780	800	828	848
T ₈ , V + P + A	350	735	815	865	902	928
CD (P = 0.05)	89.2	92.4	31.6	54.8	63.5	71.4

PSB = Phosphate solubilising bacteria, AZO = Azospirillum, VAM = Vesicular arbuscular mycorrhiza, V + P + A = VAM + PSB + AZO.

Table 5. Stevioside content of the stevia leaf

Treatments	Experiments in months					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
T ₁ , Control	2.90±0.01**	6.55±0.01**	9.50±0.02**	11.20±0.03**	11.05±0.02**	11.64±0.01**
T ₂ , PSB	2.77±0.02**	7.06±0.02**	10.47±0.01**	10.91±0.01**	11.78±0.01**	12.22±0.01**
T ₃ , AZO	3.02±0.02**	7.87±0.02**	9.91±0.03**	9.50±0.03**	9.91±0.02**	11.93±0.01**
T ₄ , VAM	1.62±0.01**	5.58±0.01**	7.91±0.01**	9.96±0.01**	10.08±0.01**	11.27±0.02**
T ₅ , V + A	2.90±0.04**	10.33±0.02**	11.34±0.02**	11.93±0.01**	12.07±0.01**	12.36±0.01**
T ₆ , P + A	3.80±0.01**	10.18±0.01**	11.78±0.01**	12.80±0.02**	12.94±0.01**	13.38±0.01**
T ₇ , V + P	2.77±0.01**	7.60±0.03**	11.78±0.01**	12.51±0.01**	13.09±0.01**	13.09±0.01**
T ₈ , V + P + A	2.26±0.02**	11.93±0.01**	13.38±0.01**	19.08±0.01**	19.40±0.01**	20.17±0.01**
CD (P = 0.05)	2.90±0.01**	6.55±0.01**	9.50±0.02**	11.20±0.03**	11.05±0.02**	11.64±0.01**

PSB = Phosphate solubilising bacteria, AZO = Azospirillum, VAM = Vesicular arbuscular mycorrhiza, V + P + A = VAM + PSB + AZO

Values are mean ± SEM. (**) P < 0.01; as compared with control treatment.

Correlation study revealed the negative effect of soil pH with sweetness intensity ($r = -0.743^{**}$) which was highly significant at 1% (Fig. 3) whereas sweet potency was also shown positive correlation with amount of stevioside present in the

extracts ($r = 0.826$) (Fig. 4). Finally, results show that the sweetness was not dependent on month wise collected samples but dependent on treatments of bio-fertilizers applied in the field and with soil pH.

Fig. 3. Mean correlation between pH and sweet potency

Fig. 4. Correlation between mean stevioside content and sweet potency.

The present results revealed that the sweetness intensity were sustainably maintained above 52 times sweeter than standard sucrose solution (3.0% w/v) throughout the 6 month of treatments with treatment eight and even the values were higher than that of other treatments and over control. Treatment with V + A, P + A and P + V where two bio-fertilizers were applied in combination, showed comparatively better results over control samples that may be due to effect of applied bio-fertilizers in acidic soil environment which enhanced the organic carbon content and other nutrient availability in soil. The present study revealed the same trend as earlier cited research work in which it was stated that organic carbon content is rich in acid soil¹⁴ and applied bio-fertilizers enhance in accumulation of sweet glycoside in leaf sample¹⁵. It was experimented on comparative relative sweetness of *Stevia* extract; aspartame and cyclamate/saccharin blend by magnitude estimation method¹³. The sweetness was largely pH dependent and acid pH favored the increase of the sweetness potency of *Stevia* extract. In our study distilled water was used for preparation of sample and standard solution which show no variation in the sweet intensity. The same study was reported earlier where tap water, distilled water and potable water were use to dissolve the various sweet samples and were compared to check the variation of sweet intensity among them^{16,17}. Hence water does not have any impact on changes of sweet intensity. Literature survey also revealed that stevioside and rebaudioside are high content of sweetness properties. Stevioside is 350 times sweeter than table sugar whereas rebaudioside is 450 times sweeter than table sugar¹⁸. Chemical nature showed that rebaudioside contains four glucose molecules whereas stevioside contains three glucose molecules hence rebaudioside is sweeter than stevioside.

Conclusion

The results suggest that improved agro-technique can improve not only the content of fresh leaf biomass of *Stevia* but also improve the percentage of stevioside content in the same. Proper extraction and refining of *Stevia* can improve the sweetness potency but the values are highly system dependent. The extent of sweetness of a compound depends

on factors like climatic conditions, geographical locations, mode of preparation of extracts, training of panelists and room environment maintained during the test. We can conclude that *Stevia* crude extract is more than 50 times sweet than sucrose (3.0%) and it can be used as natural bio sweetener for application of various food products.

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